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Paper Title : Factors Influencing Consumer Intentions to Adopt Digital Banking
Integrating UTAUT2 and Security

NIM/Lecture Code	Name	Contribution to the Paper
2540115055	Vanessa Surya	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Propose a research model and methodology- Writing the paper- Create statements and indicators in the research model- Create a Google Form questionnaire from the statements and indicators- Collecting and analyzing the data from the questionnaire
D1619	Joni Suhartono	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Provide conceptual guidance for the content of research methods- Review and provide feedback on the quality of the paper- Analyze research models and questionnaires
D5276	Lusianah	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Provide feedback on the results of data analysis using SmartPLS- Provided conceptual guidance for the content of the paper